

Teachers' Well-Being as Predictor of Job Satisfaction Among DepEd Teachers

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ABSTRACT: Educator job satisfaction has been identified as exceptionally vital in teachers' well-being and implementing any education transformation, including the teacher in life-lengthy learning, the value of the instruction-learning process, and general satisfaction with life. The disturbing note is that many of today's teachers are displeased with their employment. Nevertheless, there is a common feeling that teachers nowadays are not happy with their jobs. The main objective of this study was to determine which domain of teachers' well-being significantly predicts job satisfaction among DepEd teachers. This study employed a quantitative, non-experimental research design utilizing the causal-effect technique. A total of 204 elementary public teachers were surveyed. The study revealed that a very high level, both in teacher's well-being and job satisfaction, was interpreted as very much manifested. It further revealed that teachers' well-being significantly predicts job satisfaction of DepEd teachers. In addition, there is a significant relationship between the well-being of teachers and job satisfaction. Indeed, the well-being of teachers generates job satisfaction. It suggests that programs be implemented by the Department of Education that can offer additional relevant information on job satisfaction that will serve as a framework for policymaking and improvement initiatives and interventions to enhance the well-being of teachers.

Keywords: MAED- Educational Management, Well-being, Job satisfaction, Philippines

The job satisfaction of educators working in schools is always problematic. The troubling note is that numerous teachers nowadays are unhappy with their employment. Nevertheless, the common impression of teachers is unsatisfied with their jobs. It looks to be a growing dissatisfaction with the work they have because the educational quality is declining. It was conducted yearly since 1984, the challenges of school leaders, they surveyed 1,000 teachers and 500 principals as sampling in K-12 schools around the state. Only 39% of the teachers said they are very satisfied with their work. However, it has fallen only 23% since 2008 and has fallen 5% in the last year alone. Factors contributing to reducing job satisfaction include working in schools, where budgets, professional development opportunities, and time spent with colleagues are all on the desk (Richmond, 2013).

Teacher job satisfaction is the most important factor in implementing any educational reform, involving teachers in lifelong learning, improving teaching quality, and overall life satisfaction. Teachers are considered a key role in the development of education and the general progress of the country. They take part in an essential role in the academic achievement and success of students. Teachers who are satisfied with their work play an important role in improving society (Essays, 2018).

Well-being is also interconnected with job satisfaction. Job Satisfaction has been studied as a measure of happiness, including emotions, interpersonal satisfaction, goals achieved, self-concept, and self-perceived ability to cope with daily life. According to the 2019 survey in the United Kingdom, 50% of teachers are dissatisfied with their work, reporting 24% interpreted as low or 26% interpreted as a medium level of satisfaction. Given that full-time employees spend most of their daily lives at work, their low well-being at work may partially simplify the low satisfaction of their job. Thus, Job satisfaction is related to one's life contentment as it affects the person's social, physical, and mental health. It is a vital element to evaluate the person's satisfaction towards his or her job that eventually influences personal and organizational development. This signifies the achievements such as recognition, good pay, promotion, communication with supervisors, job security, and others lead to one's job satisfaction (Xiaoyan, 2016).

In the light of the aforementioned, studies on both teachers' well-being and job satisfaction were done in various parts of the world. However, the researcher has not come across the study of the influence of teachers' well-being and job satisfaction on the local setting. Career teaching causes burnout due to high workloads. Most teachers go through high work pressure, which affects their well-being. This situation encouraged the researcher to perform a study on teachers' well-being. The administrators, teachers, and students at DepEd will make the study socially significant. The results of this study will support our teachers and students involved in this study mainly as the teachers play an essential role in supplying the students with quality education. Suppose these goals and aspirations are fulfilled and realized. In that case, it will bring a positive bearing on society because teachers and students are part and parcel of the social process,

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the prime movers of the progressive change in society, and serve as a valuable human resource in fulfilling the dream and purpose of society and achieving long-term goals. Therefore, this research is urgently needed.

Research Objectives

The main purpose of this research was to determine which domain of teachers' well-being significantly predicts job satisfaction among DepEd teachers. Specifically, it took to achieve the following objectives.

1. To describe the level of teacher's well-being among DepEd teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 Workload;
 - 1.2 Organizational; and
 - 1.3 Students' Interaction.
2. To describe the level of job satisfaction of teachers in terms of:
Security;
 - 2.1 Work Environment;
 - 2.2 Job Responsibilities; and
 - 2.3 Community Attachments/ Linkages.
3. To find out the significant relationship between teachers' well-being and job satisfaction among DepEd teachers.
4. To determine which domains of teachers' well-being significantly predict job satisfaction among DepEd teachers.

Hypothesis

1. The null hypotheses were tested at a significance level of 0.05.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers' well-being and job satisfaction among DepEd teachers.
3. There is no domain of teachers' well-being that significantly predicts job satisfaction among DepEd teachers.

I. Review of Related Literature

Teachers' Well Being

The focus on teacher well-being is to help the individual and learning environments to face the high demands in teaching-learning of the institution. Focusing on well-being gives the teachers the depth and positivity to challenge and innovate the strategies of working without burning out or giving up. It is assumed that a cheerful person is endowed with an optimistic character, tend to see the bright side of things, and does not dwell excessively on negative things, and lives in a developed society, and has the resources in achieving essential goals (Kinman, 2020).

While studies on teacher's perceptions of student interactions with teachers demonstrate a link between the views and teacher well-being, having a good face to face interaction with students like expressing their concerns and Positive interactions with the teacher can be motivating behind the devotion of teachers to the teaching profession, particularly the preservice stage. Conversely, instructors' perceptions of complicated teacher-students' interactions, especially in unorganized classrooms, may also be correlated with the strain and exhausted feelings. And instructors who had been faced with disruptive students pronounced feeling emotionally exhausted and had extra terrible attitudes closer to their students (Claessens et al., 2016).

Meanwhile, bodily well-being, like feeling very healthful and active for public fitness purposes, is likewise regarded as essential to typical well-being. Well-being is related to more than one fitness, job, own circle of relatives, and economically associated benefits. Individuals with excessive tiers of well-being are extra running difficult than getting suitable effects at paintings and are much more likely to contribute to their communities (Diener & Tov, 2015). Moreover, there may be no popular settlement around an unmarried definition of well-being. However, there may be a consensus at minimal wherein well-being entails the presence of superb feelings and moods like contentment, happiness, and the absence of terrible feelings, including depression, anxiety, having delight with lifestyles, success, and superb functioning. In easy terms, well-being may be defined as superbly judging lifestyles and feeling suitable approximately it (Veenhoven, 2010).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction lets individuals experience a positive emotional response when doing their job or when they are present at work. Job satisfaction surveys are becoming a staple in most working environments as leading organizations measure this form of feeling. In addition, job satisfaction statistics reveal that there is an average upward curve as most employees are happy with where they work. An estimated 54% of respondents say that they are satisfied, according to the Conference Board's survey of approximately 2,000 U.S. employees. It is the highest number in the last two decades.

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Contributing factors involve better commutes, the working environment, job security, colleagues, and the nature of the work itself (BasuMallick, 2020).

Moreover, job satisfaction can also be related to one's life contentment as it affects the person's health in social, physical, and mental aspects. It is a relevant element to examine the person's satisfaction towards his or her job satisfaction that eventually affects personal and organizational development. This means that achievements such as recognition, good pay, promotion, communication with supervisor, job security, and others lead to one's job satisfaction (Xiaoyan Gu, 2016).

In the study, that instructors assigned in public colleges had better task pride than the ones running in non-public colleges, and there has been a statistically substantial distinction among those businesses of instructors ($p < .05$). On the opposite hand, instructors assigned in non-public college on contractual foundation and their contracts are prolonged yearly consistent with their performance. For those reasons, instructors need to acquire a first-rate fulfillment of their job satisfaction and enhance and renew themselves to live in identical colleges for any other year. It negatively affected the job satisfaction of instructors running in non-public colleges. It changed into determined that instructors' job satisfaction differs in age, and it changed into statistically substantial ($p < .01$). Educators on the age of fifty-one (51) and above had better job satisfaction levels than the lecturers in different age businesses (Nigama et al. 2018).

II. METHOD

The methodologies and processes that used in this study are described in this chapter. It consists of research design, population and samples, research instruments, data collection, and statistical tools.

Research Design

This study utilized a non-experimental, quantitative research design using causal-effects techniques and regression analysis. Researchers use surveys to collect data to test hypotheses. These data are production statistics. This research design applies to this research because its purpose is to figure out a relationship between teachers' well-being and job satisfaction. In addition, the variables in this study, teachers' well-being, and job satisfaction, are checked in their natural environment, so it is not experimental, so they cannot be manipulated or modified.

Furthermore, causal effect was used to determine what domains of teachers' wellbeing best influence job satisfaction among DepEd teachers in Maco District. In general, this study has independent and dependent variables. Without altering the independent variable, the causal-effect approach is used to examine the effects of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Research Locale

This study was carried out primarily in the Republic of the Philippines, Province of Davao De Oro, Maco District. The respondents were the elementary teachers of the Maco District, which contribute to their job satisfaction through the well-being of teachers and allowed researchers to receive respondents, gather information quickly, and carry out these research topics.

Population and Sample

The research was conducted at the 38 public elementary schools in the Maco District. There were four hundred and forty-five (445) respondents listed from 207 primary teachers in the public primary school using the Raosoft. Calculator program. From the varied experiences of teachers' well-being and job satisfaction, they have been identified to give enough information in relation to the current investigation, which is to determine the influence of teachers' well-being on the job satisfaction of DepEd teachers. The researcher utilized simple random sampling in determining the number of teachers per school. To determine the appropriate respondents for the study, the rule of thumb was followed. In quota sampling, the researcher prefers to work with the proper sample per stratum. (Bentler & Yuan, 1999)

The inclusion criteria for this study include: the study respondents were male and female teachers in identified public elementary schools within the Maco District and are permanent teachers. They are the ones that suit the sample respondents and offer valuable knowledge to test the hypotheses of this study. It excludes parents, pupils, school heads, and DepEd officials, and hence this study focused on the well-being of teachers and job satisfaction among DepEd teachers. Respondents may withdraw at any time if they feel threatened by the conduct of the research.

Research Instrument

The study utilized two sets of downloaded and modified survey questionnaires. It composed of two parts. The first set was used to determine the level of teachers' well-being and job satisfaction. The second set was used to determine the relationship of the variables and their influence.

The first part is adapted from the study of Rebecca J. Collie entitled "Understanding, Teacher Well-being and Motivation, Measurement, Theory, and Change over time (Collie et al., 2015). The survey is composed of three (3) indicators with 16 item- statements. The downloaded questionnaire was modified to fit a school environment. Experts

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validated the redesigned questionnaire, and pilot testing was conducted. In determining the level of Teachers' well-being, the following parameter limits were employed.

While the second part of the survey was the job satisfaction questionnaire which pertained to determining the level of teachers' leadership practices of Job Satisfaction. The adapted questionnaire was from Calaguas (2017) Standardized Survey-Questionnaire from Asia Pacific Institute of Advanced Research. The survey is composed of four (4) indicators with 40 item-statements. It was modified and compressed to contextualize the school setting. The redesigned questionnaire was evaluated by specialists and pilot tested. The following parameter limits were used in the level of job satisfaction.

III. RESULTS

This chapter discusses data and results in analysis based on study findings. The following topics are covered in the discussion: teachers' well-being, work satisfaction, the significance of the link between teachers' well-being and job satisfaction, and the considerable effect of teacher well-being on job satisfaction.

The observed standard deviation ranged from 0.53 to 0.97, which is smaller than the standard deviation of the Likert scale. The scores obtained in this study are close to the average, indicating that there is a change in the respondents (Wittink & Bayer, 1994).

Level of Teachers' Well-Being

Table 1 presents the study's findings on the level of well-being of teachers. With a standard deviation of 0.38, the level of teachers' well-being has an average mean of 4.49 or very high. This means that teachers' well-being is very much manifested all the time.

From this finding, *student interaction well-being* has the highest mean score of 4.62 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.42. This was followed by *organizational interaction well-being*, which had a mean rating of 4.49 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.45. The lowest mean score is *workload well-being* with a mean rating of 4.34 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.50. The overall total level of teachers' well-being is very high, implying that teachers pay close attention to their own happiness. It means that teachers are emotionally healthy, capable of managing time and coping with stress, and have a positive attitude about their jobs.

Table 1

Level of Teachers' Well-Being

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Levels
Workload Well-being	4.34	0.50	Very High
Organizational Well-being	4.49	0.45	Very High
Student Interaction Well-being	4.62	0.42	Very High
Overall	4.49	0.38	Very High

Level of Job Satisfaction of Teachers

Table 2 shows the second objective of this research, which is to determine the teacher's job satisfaction level, measured by a questionnaire with the following indicators: *Security, Work Environment, Job Responsibilities, and Community Attachments/ Linkages*. The computations on the overall level of job satisfaction revealed a grand mean of 4.30 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.39. This indicates that the item statements stated in the *job satisfaction of teachers* are manifested all the time.

The indicators that contributed to teachers' very high level of job satisfaction have a rating that ranges from 4.13 to 4.48. First, *Security* got the highest mean score of 4.48 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.48. Second is the *Work Environment* with a mean score of 4.35 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.35. Third, *Job Responsibilities* got a mean score of 4.24 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.38. Fourth, *Community Attachments/ Linkages* got the lowest mean score of 4.13 or high with a standard deviation of 0.56.

The overall level of job satisfaction of DepEd teachers is very high, which means that the item statements for job satisfaction of DepEd teachers are observed at all times. This also shows that teachers in the classroom are incredibly efficient and effective. Because they are delighted with their tasks, teachers are invested in successfully educating their students.

Table 2
Level of Job Satisfaction of DepEd Teachers

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Levels
security	4.48	0.48	Very High
Work Environment	4.35	0.48	Very High
Job Responsibilities	4.24	0.38	Very High
Community Attachments/ Linkages	4.13	0.56	High
Overall	4.30	0.39	Very High

Significance on the Relationship between Teachers' Well-being and Job Satisfaction of DepEd Teachers

As shown in Table 3, the p-value is less than 0.05, and there is a significant relationship between teachers' well-being and job satisfaction. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected; that is, there is no significant relationship between teachers' well-being and job satisfaction among DepEd teachers. This further means that teachers; well-being has a significant impact on job satisfaction among DepEd teachers. More specifically, the study found a positive and significant relationship between teacher's well-being and job satisfaction among DepEd teachers.

It could be noted that teachers' well-being is a factor that contributes to job satisfaction among DepEd teachers. These observable reasons note that teachers' well-being has an impact on DepEd instructors' job satisfaction. Job satisfaction contributes to a person's overall well-being.

When the domains of *teachers' well-being* were correlated with the overall *job satisfaction*, data showed that *Workload Well-being* was significantly correlated with *job satisfaction* of DepEd teachers since the results showed an r-value of 0.323 with the probability value of $p < 0.05$ or *significant*. *Organizational Well-being* was significantly correlated with *job satisfaction* of DepEd teachers since the results revealed an r-value of 0.270 with the probability value of $p < 0.05$ or *significant*. *Student Interaction Well-being* was also significantly correlated with *job satisfaction* of DepEd teachers since the results showed an r-value of 0.236 with the probability value of $p < 0.05$ or *significant*.

Table 3
Significance on the Relationship between Teachers' Well-being and Job Satisfaction of DepEd Teachers

Teachers' Well-being	r-value	r-squared	p-value	Decision
Workload Well-being	0.323*	1.043	0.001	Reject Ho
Organizational Well-being	0.270*	0.0729	0.001	Reject Ho
Student Interaction Well-being	0.236*	0.0557	0.001	Reject Ho

* $p < 0.05$

Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Teachers' Well-Being to Job Satisfaction of DepEd Teachers

Table 4 shows the regression coefficients, which are used to test the significant impact of overall teacher's well-being on the job satisfaction of DepEd teachers. Using regression analysis, the data show that overall teacher well-being significantly affects teacher job satisfaction because the impact value for teacher well-being is 8.929, and the p-value is 0.001. This means that the teachers' well-being significantly influences the job satisfaction of teachers since the probability value is lower than the standard set in this study which is $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.116 implies that the 11.6% of the job satisfaction of teachers was due to the variation in teachers' well-being. The remaining 88.4% is influenced by the other factors not covered in this study. The $P < 0.05$ signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis set in the early part of this study.

In particular, the data showed that the well-being of teachers significantly influences DepEd teachers' work satisfaction. This was a workload with a beta in standardized coefficients of 0.241, which has a probability value of 0.004 less than an

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alpha value of 0.05 or less. However, organizational well-being has a beta coefficient of 0.096 with a probability value of 0.305, and student interaction well-being has a beta coefficient of 0.051 with a probability value of 0.563, which may influence the job satisfaction of DepEd teachers with the support of other indicators.

Table 4
Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Teachers' Well-Being to Job Satisfaction of DepEd Teachers

Interpersonal Competence	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	2.901	0.306				
Workload Well-being	0.185	0.064	0.241*	2.916	0.004	Reject Ho
Organizational Well-being	0.083	0.081	0.096	1.029	0.305	Do not Reject Ho
Student Interaction Well-being	0.048	0.082	0.051	0.579	0.563	Do not Reject Ho
Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction						
R =	0.341*	F-ratio	=	8.929		
R ² =	0.116	P-value	=	0.001		

IV. DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the discussion, conclusions, and recommendations based on the findings of the study. The study's main purpose was to determine which domain of teachers' well-being significantly influences job satisfaction among DepEd teachers. The discussion in this chapter is organized according to each research objective and supported with related literature.

Level of Teachers' Wellbeing

The overall level of teachers' well-being is very high, which means that teachers' well-being is very much observed by the teachers. It implies that teachers are emotionally healthy, handle time successfully, cope with pressures, and have a good attitude about work. This research is also related to the statement that the well-being of teachers is reflected in a positive teaching attitude. This arises from the caring relationship with colleagues and students, the belief that a person can teach effectively, and the personal feeling and professional that responds to the needs and expectations (How to Grow Teacher Wellbeing in Your Schools, 2019).

Similarly, focusing on wellness provides teachers with the strength and optimism to challenge and change work strategies without getting burned out or giving up. People who mean well-being have the following points: a cheerful personality, they like to look on the good side, not think about bad things, live in an economically developed society, confident and have sufficient resources to advance in the achievement of valuable goals. However, it should be noted that with the rapid development of research on subjective well-being, the description of happy people is changing (Looking After Teacher Wellbeing, 2020).

In addition, this research is also supported by Roberts and Monday (2019), who believe that health is not just about being free from disease, stress, or even satisfaction. This is about the fuller prosperity of teachers. Teacher happiness can be described as 'you are free to use your creativity to support your student's success'. They can learn and develop their careers and receive their rewards. They have a support network to help them overcome their challenges.

Level of Job Satisfaction

The overall level of job satisfaction of DepEd teachers is very high, which means that the item statements for job satisfaction of DepEd teachers are observed at all times. This further suggests that teachers in class have very good efficiency and effectiveness. Teachers are involved in successfully educating their students because they are pleased with their assignments.

This finding is consistent with Suriansyah and Aslamiah (2018), which links teacher job satisfaction to their behavior and teaching profession. It also guarantees the quality of education, where the quality assurance of education affects the effectiveness of education. In terms of student success and teacher performance, teacher job satisfaction is strongly related to teacher professional success. Teachers with low satisfaction will lead to lower student performance and increase absenteeism. Students will lack creativity and frustration, leading to their poor performance.

The study also of Polarcán (2018) audit report found that building a strong school culture of support, trust, fairness, and communication was important to ensuring teacher job satisfaction. In addition, teachers' beliefs about their professional abilities and mental health are seen as important factors affecting their job satisfaction.

The similar results of job satisfaction and lifelong learning ability of English teachers are relatively high. There were no significant differences in job satisfaction and lifelong learning abilities of English teachers in terms of gender, work experience, and school type. Yenen (2018) said that studies show that there is a positive, medium, and essential relationship between job satisfaction and key abilities for lifelong learning, and job satisfaction does not have a significant predictor of performance on lifelong learning.

Significance on the Relationship between Teachers' Well-being and Job Performance of DepEd Teachers

The correlation between teacher well-being and teacher job satisfaction shows a highly significant relationship. This implies that the well-being of teachers is correlated with the job satisfaction of DepEd teachers. It also means that the well-being of teachers affects the job satisfaction of DepEd teachers. According to Muniandy (2017), job satisfaction helps develop happiness. As with any other job, a teacher must saturate her work to achieve a successful career. Happiness in life encompasses all aspects of an individual's entire life. An individual's high level of job satisfaction positively affects both job performance and life satisfaction.

Additionally, many studies have focused on teacher happiness and job satisfaction. The relationship between job satisfaction and teacher happiness correlates with both the optimal measure of job satisfaction and happiness at work. Sirona (2019) mentioned that after managing the role of the socioeconomic profile of interviewed individuals, the results confirm a strong and positive impact of job satisfaction on teachers' health.

In addition, the correlation between happiness and job satisfaction among English teachers at one of the Malaysian public universities analyzed that the teachers have a high level of job satisfaction and psychological well-being. Mohan (2015) posited that research has shown that academics in public and private universities in Malaysia are moderately satisfied with their work.

Regression Analysis on the Domains of Influence of Teachers' Well-being and Job Performance of DepEd Teachers

The influence of teachers' well-being on DepEd teacher job satisfaction was studied using regression analysis. The results indicated that DepEd teachers' work satisfaction was strongly correlated with their general well-being. Of the three areas of teachers' well-being, there is only one indicator that significantly affects DepEd teacher job satisfaction: workload health status. This means that if the teacher's well-being is very high, the teacher's job satisfaction is very high. The workload is one of the primary predictors of job satisfaction, based on the result of the study. The results indicated that workload health has a substantial impact on DepEd teachers' job satisfaction. However, organizational well-being and the well-being of interactions with students can also affect job performance, but with support from other indicators.

Based on the result of the study of ZamanianSarvestani, Sedaghati, Ghatmiri, and Kouhnavard (2016), the job satisfaction of employees is determined by the load provided by the organization. The amount of work affects job satisfaction. Excessive work reduces employee satisfaction, so inventorying employee workload can increase work satisfaction. A variety of requirements are defined as workloads, including quantitative, qualitative, mental, and physical manipulations.

On the other hand, Kokoroko and Sanda (2019) say that workload is the level of processing power exerted at work, reflecting the needs of a person's energy supply and work. The task reflects the difficulty of the task and can contain any variable. A task is the total amount of work that people must complete in a specified time. A workload refers to the amount of focus necessary to achieve performance goals impacted by the job's needs and experience. A workload is the number of resources needed to complete an allocation and the number of resources required for a sequence of concurrent activities.

V. Conclusions

Grounded on the research results, conclusions are strained to answer the sub-question raised in the previous chapter. The respondents from the province of Davao de Oro, Maco District teachers are in a very level of performance in terms of well-being which means that they are excellent when it comes to workload well-being, organizational well-being, and students' interactions well-being. On the other hand, DepEd teachers' overall level of job satisfaction is very high, which means they showed very high in terms of security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community attachments

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and linkages. Based on the research results, the conclusions are strained by answering the sub-questions raised in the previous chapter. Maco District Teachers were the respondents that have shown a very high level of well-being. It means that they are excellent in workload well-being, organizational well-being, and student interaction well-being. On the other hand, DepEd teachers' overall job satisfaction was very high, which proved to be very high in terms of security, work environment, job responsibilities, community attachment, and linkages. Furthermore, the study discovered that teachers' well-being significantly correlated with job satisfaction. In the same way, there is a significant influence of teachers' well-being on job satisfaction. It shows that the results among the two variables are statistically very highly remarkable. As a result, in its unique capacity, the domain workload well-being may become the best measure of job satisfaction. Further, organizational well-being and students' interaction well-being can also be a predictor of job satisfaction but with the help of other indicators.

VI. Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions made, the researchers make the following recommendations.

The study revealed a very high level of teachers' well-being, including its indicators, workload well-being, organizational well-being, and students' interaction well-being. Teachers' well-being showed a very high level of well-being. It is indicative to continue promoting positive relationships in the workplace that develop the teacher's motivation and productivity and develop the well-being of teachers by creating a positive and collaborative working environment where teachers feel supportive value. Moreover, workload well-being recognizes as the lowest indicator. It is recommended to lessen teachers from clerical tasks or administrative tasks.

On the other hand, DepEd teachers' job satisfaction got a very high description, including its indicators, security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community attachments/linkages. It is suggested that DepEd officials should intensify the reward, recognition, promotion, job security, and other motivational factors that will satisfy the teachers of their job. It was discovered that community attachments/linkage is the lowest indicator in job satisfaction of DepEd teachers. It is indicative that to increase the partnership and linkages to the local government unit, private institutions, and the community.

In addition, there is a significant relationship between the well-being of teachers and job satisfaction. Indeed, the well-being of teachers generates job satisfaction. Job performance, life satisfaction, and the well-being of people are greatly influenced by a high degree of job satisfaction. The researcher also advises that teachers need to consistently develop their well-being by conducting leisure events and workshops. Teachers should discover creative ways of enhancing their well-being, such as maintaining a healthy attitude, connecting to colleagues, doing yoga, and exercising physically. The higher level of health and well-being of teachers will enhance educational performance for students. A good teacher with strong morale and high job satisfaction is more likely to deliver lessons that help students do better in the lessons in an innovative, engaging and successful way.

The result revealed that teachers' well-being significantly influences the job satisfaction of DepEd teachers. The data, in its singularity, shows that workload well-being has a considerable impact on DepEd instructors' job satisfaction. Therefore, researchers are encouraged to develop a program that allows the Department of Education to provide additional information related to job satisfaction which will serve as a basis for policymaking and intervention plans and strategies to improve teachers' well-being.

Subsequently, although the findings of the Department of Education show that teachers' job satisfaction has a significant impact on teacher well-being, researchers recommend that further investigations regarding other factors related to teacher happiness be conducted. Further studies are likely to be conducted to confirm the findings of the current study, which is likely to be a multivariate analysis to further the findings of the study.

The outcome showed that the well-being of teachers affects DepEd teachers' job satisfaction. In its specific skill, the finding highlights that workload well-being affects DepEd teachers' job satisfaction significantly. The researcher, therefore, suggests that programs be implemented by the Department of Education that can offer additional relevant information on job satisfaction that will serve as a framework for policymaking and improvement initiatives and interventions to enhance the well-being of teachers.

Subsequently, since the study result indicates a substantial effect on the well-being of teachers on the job satisfaction of DepEd teachers, the researcher suggests that more research should be carried out on other factors correlated with the well-being of teachers. To verify the findings of the current study, additional research should be carried out. This could be a qualitative, mixed-method, or multi-variate analysis to deepen the findings of the study.

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